

BUILDING BRAND EQUITY USING ADVERGAMES EXPERIENCES: A BRAZILIAN STUDY CASE

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Abstract

In the light of relative failures in the early forms of online ads, advergames have increasingly been used as part of a marketing campaign to promote products and brands. Despite growing popularity, their efficacy it's yet to be thoroughly proved and very little is known about the building of attitudes towards advergames, especially in emerging economies such as Brazil – Latin America's leader of Internet users, ahead of both Argentina and Mexico. Since the human being does not separate emotion from cognition even when using or buying a product, concepts like feelings, emotions, experience, pleasure and beauty have become more relevant in design and marketing research. Moreover, early studies suggest that digital games can bring up different kinds of experiences to their users. Those experiences were divided into six categories: experiences related to the senses; experiences related to the feelings; social experiences; cognitive experiences; use experiences; and motivational experiences. Supported by a focus group technique, the objectives of our study were to refine and empirically test the six categories of experiences framework using a case study of online advergames; to identify which experiences are generated by advergames and whether they promoted brand recall, a common measure of brand equity among Brazilian students. This paper sets out to show that design experiences can increase advergames effectiveness more than classical advertising ads in building brand equity.

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Introduction

The constant and rapid changes in the contemporary market environment require a great integration between consolidated disciplines, such as design, information technology and marketing. The success in a complex market will be achieved by those companies that provide experiences for their customers, mainly supported by tools such as information technology and the integration between communication and entertainment (Schmitt, 1999, p. 38).

Cartellieri et al. (2001) argues that technology is providing new types of interaction between businesses and consumers. Among these changes, the experiential content, through the Experiential Marketing and Design, allows consumers to experience the idea of owning a product, service or brand. The Experiential Marketing was developed in the 80's and was consolidated by Schmitt (1999). The Experiential Design ideas emerged some years later, concentrated mainly in works focused on product design, such as Jordan (2002), Jääskö et al. (2003), Desmet (2002) and Norman (2004).

Experience grew in importance and influenced the market through design and marketing. It is therefore essential to promote research in order to identify the degree of influence experience has in the interaction with consumers. One of the new points of convergence between technology, design, marketing and experience is advergame.

The purpose of this study was to investigate whether design experiences can increase advergames effectiveness and build brand equity. The objective was to test the six categories of experiences framework using online advergames as research objects, to identify which experiences were generated by advergames and if they promoted brand recall.

This research was developed based on a qualitative approach, and its nature was exploratory. Because this is a rather new subject in the theoretical field, particularly in Brazil, the focus group technique was used to collect and discuss players' opinions concerning advergames. The research was designed in three stages: planning, focus group session and opinions analysis.

The sample was composed of 10 advertising students. All of them previously received a list of 19 advergames – selected at researchers' convenience. The students had a week to play and explore all the games. The focus group session took place on February 25th, and lasted almost an hour and a half. It was recorded with the students' authorization.

Content analysis was used at this stage to register the main dimensions referred by the students interviewed. The analysis units were phrases that represented the theme. Then, these phrases were compared to the framework proposed by Buccini and Padovani (2006).

Design and Experience

It seems a fact that users buy products not only based on reason but also on emotions. According to Norman (2004), “the emotional side of design may be more critical to a product’s success than its practical elements”. This reveals that besides searching for aspects related to the product’s functional performance, users also search for pleasure when using it (Norman, 2004; Jordan, 2003). Regardless the type of the product, projecting the experience in a positive and efficient way is the new challenge for designers.

Defining Experience

According to Csikszentmihalyi’s (1991) definition anything that makes life more valuable and pleasant is called “flow”. It is something beyond the satisfaction of basic needs. It goes further the limits of stimulus-response reactions and it is related to positive experiences and to the enjoyment of life. The “flow” acts through the senses, the thought, the body in flow, through other people and work as flow. It can be understood, therefore, as the key to personal human experiences.

In this study, experience is understood as an individual phenomenon which occurs in a person’s mind as a result of the processing of a complex number of internal and external stimuli- outer and inner- and that depends on one’s subjective interpretations.

Experiential Design

The experiential design considers all kinds of experiences a user might have when interacting with a product. It seeks not only to fulfill the user’s urgent and objective needs, but also to understand and accomplish the human motivations and aspirations related to a product. The factors related to experience are very subjective and depend on dynamic aspects hard for the professional to foresee and measure such as: past experiences, taste and ideas that change with time and personal life situations (Jääskö et al., 2003).

The AIGA Experience Design (2001) study group defines the following characteristics of Experiential Design:

- It has a broader approach than the traditional design and aims to create experiences, rather than simply products and services;
- It visualizes the entire lifecycle of a product;
- It creates a relationship with individuals and not with a mass of consumers;
- It cares to create an environment that connects the user emotionally;
- It is based on both traditional disciplines, and also on fields never before used in the creation of products, services and environments.

Experiences Categories

Based on the theories of Jordan (2001), Norman (2004) and Schmitt (2000), Buccini and Padovani (2007a) have distinguished six main experience categories (table 1) that are part of a framework which has proved to be an important tool to identify how each type of experience is performed in the interaction between the user and a product, as well as the result of this relation (Buccini and Padovani, 2007b). Each category has different origins and results. However, many times they occur simultaneously, making differentiation difficult.

Experiences related to the senses
Experiences related to the feelings
Social experiences
Cognitive experiences
Use experiences
Motivational experiences

Table 1: Categories of experiences (Buccini and Padovani, 2007a).

The most basic experiences are those related to the senses. They happen faster and instinctively, having low cognitive performance. These experiences are straightly related to the sensory organs and also to sexuality. The experiences related to the feelings are emotional reactions originated from the use of a product. This category is very subjective, varying a lot from person to person. Social experiences happen among individuals and are intermediated by products. Cognitive experiences are related to the thought and to the user's interpretation of the codes. The category of use experiences concerns the usability and functionality of the products. Finally, the motivational experiences, derived from the experiential action module of Schmitt's

experiential marketing theory, which refers to the owning or use of a product as being able to produce certain behaviors.

Advergame

Chen and Ringel (2001) define advergame as the use of interactive game technology to lead advertising messages to the consumer (p. 45). This way of promoting a product or brand emerged in the beginning of the 80's in home consoles such as Atari, one of the early examples is the Kool aid-man by Kraft Food that can be seen in figure 1 (Petitinga Junior, 2006). Nowadays, advergame is the fastest growing type of marketing approach in the world. The strategy of advergames is to blur the borderline between entertainment and persuasion (Dahl et al., 2006; Grigorovici and Constantin, 2004). This rapid popularization of advergames is due, mainly, to the low response that the banners and other conventional ad formats have on the web (Dahl et al., 2006).

Figure 1: Kool aid-man, one of the first advergames, sponsored by Kraft Food to Atari consoles.

Electronic games may promote a brand in different levels, from a simple signature on the corner of the screen, to the use of a product as part of the game. Petitinga Junior (2006) states that advergaming should be planned as part of a complex campaign, which involves understanding the possibilities of integration between electronic games and brands, and the most appropriated format to the target. But the most important feature of an advergame is to be fun and playable.

Several pieces of research indicate that advergames may potentially increase the appreciation of a brand, which positively impact on many of the traditional measurements of brand equity. These studies also suggest that a highly interactive and animated ad format could be expected to have a greater impact on brand equity than traditional banner advertising. Part of the appeal of this type of ad is the amount of time that users spend interacting with advergames and being exposed to brands. Thus it is the continuous and repetitive exposure to the advergames that

favors a brand recall. That clearly gives a distinct advantage to advergame over other forms of advertising (Deal, 2005).

Brand Equity

Brand management is currently one of the most important business priorities. The brand can help companies to differentiate their products and services from other companies' offers, and to gain competitive advantage (Fill, 2002, Carpenter et al., 2001; Porter, 1999).

Even being closely related, a brand and a product differ. The company manufactures a product, but consumers buy a brand, which gives meaning to a product, revealing its different functional, experiential and symbolic facets (Tavares, 1998).

The brand helps company to attract new customer. It works as a reminder and acts as an emotional bond with the client, helping him with his final decision in the purchase process. (Rust et al., 2001; Cunha et al., 1997). The challenge of building a strong brand for design and marketing professionals is to ensure that customers have experiences with products or services - through wishes, feelings, images, beliefs, perceptions, and opinions, among other thoughts - that are some way connected to the brand (Hoeffler and Keller, 2002). According to Aaker (1998), strong brand connections with costumers may increase the chances of recognizing it and taking it into consideration while purchasing.

A strong brand is strongly related to building brand equity. For Aaker (1998), brand equity is a multidimensional concept, consisting of loyalty, awareness, perceived quality, associations and other brand's assets. In general, it means that brand equity depends on customers to make a positive and strong association related to a brand, perceiving superior quality and become loyal to the company's brand. Yoo et al. (2000) claims that strengthening these dimensions, brand equity can be created, maintained and expanded.

This paper focuses on the brand awareness dimension, which measures the brand accessibility to the costumer's memory. This dimension can be measured through brand recall or brand recognition. Brand recall reflects the ability of consumers to retrieve the brand from memory when given the product category or some other type of probe like a cue; brand recognition reflects the ability of consumers to confirm prior exposure to the brand (Tavares, 1998; Hoeffler and Keller, 2002; Shimp, 2002; Chandon, 2003). According to Aaker (1998), brand awareness is a fundamental dimension to brand equity since customers tend to buy known brands because they feel comfortable with what they perceive as familiar, reliable, and having a higher quality.

Analysis

Figure 2: Coca-cola Super Coach advergence.

According to the participants the experiences related to the visual aesthetics are not as important as the gameplay. In fact, they were indifferent to that kind of characteristic. They did not complain about it and neither mentioned any game that had caught their attention by the visual aspects. However, they mentioned that sometimes the visual presentation related to the brand was annoying and disturbing, as in Coca-cola's games (Figure 2). They argued the interface had too many red objects.

Music and sound elements, in the senses category, were considered important items, particularly when evaluated as connected to the game and part of the action. The players said that without sound the game was no fun at all. An example is the game for Fox series 'Dexter', in which the player has to move a knife without cutting off his finger. Whenever the knife hit a finger a scream could be heard and that was considered very funny by the participants. Another game that was reminded by its sound was the Crazy Frog advergence by Tilibra. In the game the players had to jump from a long play to another, switching over the music, as in a remix.

Figure 3: Peta's advergaming, the 'Kentucky Fried Cruelty'.

In the experiences related to the feelings category, the players cited two advergaming games that reminded them of games they used to play when they were kids. One of them was Peta's advergaming game: the 'Kentucky Fried Cruelty' (Figure 3) concerned with animal mistreatment denunciation against the Kentucky Fried Chicken – KFC. This game had the same structure, rules and visual characteristics as the 'Mario Bros' videogame. The other was the Microsoft Live Search Maps' advergaming game that reminded them of 'PacMan'. Another highlight about feelings experiences was the user's identification with the game character. For example, in the MTV's advergaming game, called 'Me', the user could make his own avatar. One participant said: 'it was like you controlling yourself'.

Social experiences were not perceived in the games. However, the users said they shared those advergaming games with their friends by e-mail and even competed for the best scores.

The cognitive experience was very important to determine if the game was successful or not. The players refused the games that were difficult to understand, even if they had positive features as a good interface and gameplay. For example, the game 'Milk Matters' by Cravendale Milk had a very interesting and different interface, but it was considered one of the worst games by the players (Figure 4). They said it was neither possible to understand what they should do while playing or what the game was about.

Figure 4: 'Milk Matters' by Cravendale Milk.

The use experience was considered the most important aspect according to the members of the focus group. The game could not be too difficult to play, neither too easy. As advergames are casual games, their rules must be simple, cannot have many commands, a match cannot last very long, and they need to be loaded fast. One of the participants said that if a game took too long to load on the screen he would close the window and would do something else. The game 'Halo Fore', that promoted 'Halo 3', was criticized because it was very difficult to play.

The motivational experiences are associated to stimulus that interferes in the user's lifestyle. Mostly, every advergame has for main objective persuading the user to do something such as buying a product, dressing in some way, doing exercise, drinking milk etc. Among the advergames analyzed, the ones by Coca-cola stimulated some players to buy a Coke. One player said that she could not eat chicken for a week after playing the 'Kentucky Fried Cruelty' game. The players also mentioned they believed advergames could help to sell a product because users can virtually use it in a game.

Regarding brand equity, it was observed that several participants appreciated Coca-Cola's and MTV's advergames very much. They said Coca-Cola was able to transmit its brand message

and still have an enjoyable gameplay. They also perceived MTV games as educational. On the other hand, the players complained that Coca-Cola games were annoying because the red colour. The MTV game was criticised because it was hard to understand what actions the player should take to proceed with the game (Figure 5).

Figure 5: MTV Me.

Sometimes the brand recall was not effective because it was based on misunderstandings. During the focus group session, one player recalled Google Earth brand instead of the advergame supported brand, Microsoft Live Search. Probably, she might have understood the game, but did not perceive Microsoft's brand. A similar misunderstanding was noticed in to Peta's advergame. Although the game denounced animal mistreatment by KFC, except for two players, most of them thought the game was supported by KFC.

Several advergames were very effective in introducing new brands, or unknown ones, as the Pizzeria Cici,.This brand does not exist in Brazil and it is not famous, yet it was positively recalled by the players. However, the Cravendale Milk was also quite remembered, but for negative reasons. The players criticized its lack of logic, which, according to them, inhibited gameplay.

Conclusion

The main goal of this study was to identify experiences generated by advergames and verify if they promoted brand recall. Furthermore, we wanted to refine and empirically test the six categories of experiences framework using a case study of online advergames.

According to the focus group discussion about advergames content, most of the players could retrieve the brand from memory, aspect that leads to brand recall – a measurement to brand awareness.

However, one of the most used strategies in advergames to promote recall is the message repetition, often evaluated by the participants as annoying and unable to promote empathy with game users. It was also noticed that some advergames were quite recalled, but only by their negative aspects. Most of them had their gameplay criticized. So, we believe that brand recalling favors the advergame when the players have positive experiences while playing it. Additionally, in order to help building brand equity, ads and promotions should act subtle; the game design must be well constructed, aiming not to compromise the fun and gameplay.

Nevertheless, in many cases, advergame alone is not enough to promote brand recall. Most of the time, it was a consequence of several online and offline efforts. We consider that previous player's experiences with the brand and traditional ads are still fundamental to build brand equity. Also, as some players said that they shared those advergames with their friends, it suggests that advergames may work as buzz marketing and a word-of-mouth approach.

Results of the research here described reinforce the belief that design experiences can increase advergames effectiveness in building brand equity more than classical advertising ads. However, this issue requires further investigation with other groups of players.

The advergame market is growing very fast, and, as the technological features improve, more creative and innovative games must be created in the future. Academic research must try to keep up to date with the new market propositions and innovations. Moreover, we believe that experiential design studies can contribute to make advergames a better tool to disseminate thoughts and concepts related to brands and organizations.

Finally, the interactivity aspects present on advergames showed to be a characteristic that stands out in the building of positive experiences. Maybe interactivity shall become a new category of experience to be added to the framework proposed by Buccini and Padovani (2006).

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